

IMPROVED MONITORING OF URBAN RUNOFF USING REAL-TIME CONTROL SYSTEMS AND PROXY SENSING: LESSONS LEARNED FROM THREE CASE STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

Urban runoff monitoring can be significantly enhanced by making use of real-time control and advanced data analytics. This study presents models and tools developed within the EU financed project ‘StopUP’. These were applied to three case studies (CSs) and aimed at improving the detection and management of pollution events. In CS Bologna, low-cost IoT sensors were deployed at the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) and used to collect hydraulic and water quality data. The collected data were analyzed with Detrended Cross-Correlation Analysis (DCCA) and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) models and show relations between hydraulic quantities and water quality parameters, demonstrating the feasibility of low-cost proxy sensing. In the CS Wetteren, an innovative auto-sampling triggering system that integrates real-time observations, short-term rainfall predictions, and near-real-time urban runoff modeling is tested. The system demonstrates the potential of combining different data sources to refine sampling control and collect less, but more informative water quality samples. In the CS Birsfelden, pollution loads and urban runoff were approximated using online measurements of water flow and quality. These data served as a basis for operational decision-making and proactive system control to mitigate impact of pollution. The integration of predictive tools and real-time data across all three CSs supports improved identification and tracking of pollution sources. These findings suggest a promising application of real-time & proxy sensing combined with proactive control strategies for managing urban water systems under pressure.

Keywords: Sewer systems; Urban runoff; Proxy sensing; Real-time control; IoT sensors.

1. Introduction

The EU-funded Horizon Europe project Stop Urban Pollution (StopUP, <https://stopup.eu/>)-“Protecting the aquatic environment from urban runoff pollution” addresses the challenges of urban runoff pollution and its impact on aquatic environments. By developing innovative solutions to characterize, monitor, and mitigate

pollution from urban runoff and combined sewer overflows (CSOs), the project tackles a major risk to water quality in receiving bodies.

Real-time control (RTC) in sewer systems is crucial for managing the growing challenges of urban wastewater management. By dynamically adjusting the flow of wastewater in response to real-time data from sensors, RTC minimizes the risk of overflows, particularly during heavy rainfall or sudden surges in demand. This proactive approach enhances the efficiency of existing infrastructure, reducing the need for costly expansions of a sewer network. Moreover, RTC plays a vital role in protecting the environment by preventing untreated sewage from entering waterways, thus improving water quality and public health. RTC was applied in a wide range of studies related to combined sewer systems, and is becoming an essential part of sewer management plans (Saddiqi et al., 2023, van der Werf et al., 2022). RTC methodologies are data-intensive and data-dependent, and StopUP adopts low-cost sensors to measure several quantities of practical interest in sewer system management. Moreover, the development of simulations models as input for real-time control is among StopUP objectives. It is, therefore, quite natural that elements of real-time control are present in the StopUP project at various stages of development and scales.

As indicated above, the term RTC is typically used in the context of actuators that change the true state of the system, for example automatically controlling valves in a drainage network. However, it can also be used to improve monitoring efforts, used in combination with low-cost IoT sensors, also named ‘proxy sensors’. The StopUP project recognizes this need for better monitoring, and that is why RTC is implemented to improve monitoring the state of the system, i.e. diagnose which, when and where pollution occurs. The aim of this paper is twofold: i) how RTC and emerging technologies such as IoT contribute to improved monitoring, and ii) how can improved monitoring ultimately contribute to real-time control of urban (sewer) systems. In total, three case studies are presented and discussed:

- ‘Bologna’ (Italy) case study: to improve RTC, one needs to rely on actual up-to-date information of the system to be controlled. The best way to collect information is to do real-time monitoring. Unfortunately, monitoring efforts and costs greatly increase with the number of locations that need to be monitored. The aim of this case study is to reduce monitoring cost by identifying links between water quality and quantity sensors. As such, easy-to-monitor variables can be used to estimate harder-to-monitor variables, ultimately reducing the number of sensors needed to real-time monitor water quality. These proxy IoT sensors can be used to steer real-time control without the need to physically install the higher-cost sensors at the site.
- ‘Wetteren’ (Belgium) case study: The aim of this case study is to use IoT technology and an auto-sampling triggering algorithm (i.e. RTC) to improve monitoring efforts by collecting and analyzing targeted water samples. In turn, this information can aid in defining mitigation strategies in order to reduce the volume and pollutant load released to the environment.
- ‘Birsfelden’ (Switzerland) case study: RTC can be significantly improved by analyzing the information coming from improved online and offline monitoring efforts. The aim of this case study is to collect and analyze samples, using a comparable algorithm as used in the Wetteren case study, to inspect the potential of IoT sensors and data for real-time control of a storm water collection and conveyance infrastructure in a combined sewer system.

The present contribution aims to highlight the key technical and scientific elements emerging from the advancement of research on the various StopUP case studies, which contribute to improving real-time control practices in the complex management scenarios of European cities. After briefly introducing the StopUP project, it does so by presenting: a) a data-driven methodology to identify relationships between physical variables involved, in particular between hydrological variables and water quality parameters (CS Bologna); b) a novel auto-sampling triggering approach combining real-time observations, rainfall predictions, and near-real-time urban runoff modelling (CS Wetteren); c) an approach for event-based online assessment of CSO spills (CS Birsfelden).

2. The StopUP project

StopUP focuses on sustainable urban drainage systems (SuDS), rainwater (RW) management, and CSO management, integrated with the optimized use of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). It tests and demonstrates cutting-edge monitoring tools such as Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, analytical and planning technologies, and treatment solutions like constructed wetlands and filters. Using a holistic approach, StopUP

creates Urban Runoff Water Quality Management Plans (URUQMAP) to address diffuse urban pollution in six case studies (CSs) in Germany, Italy, Belgium, Norway, Switzerland, and Tunisia. The project provides guidance for improving or establishing SuDS in urban areas, while these case studies serve as models for the new water management plans. Additionally, the project helps stakeholders translate the updated Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) goals into actionable strategies. By doing so, StopUP contributes significantly to achieving the environmental quality targets set by the Water Framework Directive (WFD).

3. Case study Bologna

Real-time control involves, as a first step, identifying relationships between the various physical variables involved. In CS Bologna, correlation between time series reveals the underlying mechanism between hydrological measurements, such as rainfall and water level, and water quality parameters, such as electrical conductivity and turbidity. Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (DFA) assesses auto-correlation, but standard cross-correlation methods often yield inaccurate results due to non-stationary trends. To address this, we use Detrended Cross-Correlation Analysis (DCCA), which effectively manages non-stationarity and incorporates periodic features (Horvatic et al., 2011). DCCA was proven effective in hydrological studies (Cheng et al., 2024).

The two time series of interest are denoted by $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^m$ and $\{y_i\}_{i=1}^m$, which can be the turbidity (NTU), electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$), or water level (mm). Before using DCCA methods, we need to define the increment series R_x and R_y as

$$R_x^k = \sum_{i=1}^k x_i, \quad R_y^k = \sum_{i=1}^k y_i, \quad (1)$$

where $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Then, the whole time series is divided into $m - n$ overlapping boxes. Each box includes the $n + 1$ points sequence. Starting from the first box to the last one, we define the detrended residual as

$$f_{DCCA}^2(n, i) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{k=i}^{i+n} (R_x^k - P_{l,k,i})(R_y^k - P'_{l,k,i}), \quad (2)$$

where $P_{l,k,i}$ is the polynomial expansion with highest order l to approximate the local trend. By summing up the residuals, the cross-correlation is computed as

$$F_{DCCA-l}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{m-n} f_{DCCA}^2(n, i). \quad (3)$$

Given the F_{DCCA}^2 , the correlation coefficient $\rho(n)$ is defined upon division by the auto-correlation of two time series, $F_{DFA}(n)$, as

$$\rho(n) = \frac{F_{DCCA-l}^2}{F_{DFA}(n)F'_{DFA}(n)}. \quad (4)$$

As to the cross-correlations between water level and (a) electrical conductivity in dry season, (b) electrical conductivity in wet season, (c) turbidity during the dry season, and (d) turbidity during the wet season (Cheng et al., 2024), the results from polynomial models from 0th degree to 2nd degree (Fig. 1) are generally consistent; there is a notable negative correlation between electrical conductivity and water level, as rainwater acts as a dilution factor. However, the relationship between turbidity and water level varies by season. In the wet season, turbidity positively correlates with water level, while during the dry season, this correlation weakens significantly. Water levels influence turbidity and electrical conductivity, indicating a potential correlation between the two. The correlation coefficient provides intriguing insights, even in the absence of a strong physical relationship.

Fig. 2 depicts the relationship between electrical conductivity and turbidity, which is seen to differ between dry and wet seasons. The correlation is relatively weak, and negative, during the dry season. Notably, during the wet season, this correlation is particularly strong, with the correlation coefficient approaching minus one. During the dry season, the water level is too low to carry suspended solids or effectively dissolve chemical components. As a result, the electrical conductivity and turbidity primarily interact within the solid medium, demonstrating an unclear correlation between the two.

Fig. 1. Cross-correlation coefficients as a function of box size n (hours) for water level and (a) electrical conductivity and water level in the dry season, (b) electrical conductivity and water level in the wet season, (c) turbidity and water level in the dry season, and (d) turbidity and water level in the wet season.

Fig. 2 Cross-correlation coefficients as a function of box size n (hours) for electrical conductivity and (a) turbidity in the dry season, and (b) turbidity in the wet season.

The cross-correlation between turbidity and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) measured between September 2023 and December 2023 indicates a positive relationship (Figure 3). However, the dataset is limited, with numerous missing daily measurements. The total number of data points is fewer than 20, which is significantly lower than those available for water level, electrical conductivity (EC), and turbidity. Consequently, only a preliminary conclusion can be drawn at this stage. More robust and conclusive findings will be possible once additional data becomes available.

Fig. 3 Cross-correlation coefficients as a function of box size n (days) for COD and turbidity from Sep 2023 to Dec 2023.

Since environmental factors may not influence target measurements immediately, it is important to consider the time lag involved. For instance, when the water level rises, electrical conductivity (EC) takes time to decrease to a lower level. Therefore, studying the interactions in time series data requires attention to the correlation with lagged time series. Hence, we reproduce the DCCA algorithm with lag time series. For example, if we examine the EC with a 2-hour lag, we first shift the EC time series to $EC(t + 2h)$ and compute its correlation with the water level time series WL at time t , using the starting points $t_0 + 2h$ and t_0 . The DCCA computation follows the same methodology as outlined in the previous section. The correlations between key quantities over different time lags (h) in time series data are evaluated by the Detrended Cross-Correlation Analysis (DCCA) with a box size equal to 120 hours. The study focuses on three periods: a) May 9th-13th, 2023 (flood event), b) June 1st-5th, 2023 (typical wet period), and c) August 15th-19th, 2023 (dry period). We examined time lags from 1.25 to 6.25 hours in 1.25-hour increments; results are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Correlation coefficients between EC and turbidity vs lag h (hours) in (a) EC and Water level (b) Turbidity and Water level (c) Turbidity and EC.

During the flood and wet periods, electrical conductivity (EC) shows a negative correlation with a notable lag, peaking at around 4.5 hours. In contrast, turbidity presents a positive correlation as the lag time increases, indicating that the water level takes more time to transport solids from the bottom of the sewer pipe.

In the dry season, both EC and turbidity decrease as lag time increases. The lag effect between EC and turbidity is less pronounced during the flood and wet periods. Additionally, during the dry season, the correlation between EC and turbidity persists simultaneously. This suggests that EC and turbidity affect each other almost at the same time. Furthermore, the influence of water level on EC occurs more quickly than on turbidity.

Based on the lag effect analysis, if we intend to develop a prediction model for the relationship between water level and either EC or turbidity, it is necessary to use historical water level data from at least four hours prior. This indicates that from a mathematical viewpoint the dynamic mathematical model governing the sewer systems is not a simple ordinary differential equation (ODE) system; it requires memory data for water level, which can be represented as an integral term. In other words, the correlation analysis provides a guideline for modeling sewer systems, a concept that can be developed further.

4. Case study Wetteren

Implementing effective real-time control measures requires mapping out pollution loads and pathways. Although advancements are made in continuous water quality sensing, laboratory samples, collected with autosamplers, are still required to monitor a wide range of pollutants (e.g. PFAS/PFOS, heavy metals ...). In essence, auto-samplers need to take a number of samples that are representative for the pollution. Current monitoring efforts with auto-samplers typically occur 'offline': the set point for controlling an auto-sampler is defined by setting a threshold on a variable, measured by a sensor connected to the auto-sampler. The sampler and the operator can trade information, yet it is only available locally. This approach hinders in-depth diagnostics of the system, does not allow the use of external information, and hinders the use of more complex control algorithms; as the processing power of local units is limited. Due to advancements in robust two-way communication, IoT technology can provide real-time monitoring and control. Since an auto-sampler is in essence a pumping device, one can define the control of an auto-sampler with IoT as RTC (see introduction). As such, the continuous data stream from IoT sensors and other external data sources can be used to control and optimize the sampling.

This case study introduces a novel auto-sampling triggering approach combining real-time observations, rainfall predictions, and near-real-time urban runoff modelling. The auto-sampling trigger application integrates an auto-sampler, IoT sensors, a forecasting service, a runoff model and a server-side implementation to steer the triggering algorithm. By combining these software and hardware components, this provides a comprehensive end-to-end solution to steer effective auto-sampling strategies but also infrastructure like pumps and valves.

The remote triggering protocol includes an internal model, determining the set points for sampling (actuators) based on a model simulation and real-time observations. In this case study, a rainfall/runoff model, IoT datalogger, sensors and an auto-sampler are used (Fig. 5). The internal model defines by state model and a set point based on a threshold set on the simulated runoff (m³/s), more specifically a 'peak flow trigger'. The runoff is simulated by using a calibrated unit hydrograph as rainfall/runoff model and a rainfall forecast as input. The system is running on a service, employing an MQTT broker to support bi-directional communication between the service and the IoT logger. An MQTT broker is an IT component that uses subscriptions to so-called 'topics' to define which data from different data producers should go to the different data consumers. This makes it possible to use (real-time) measurements from the IoT logger (or other loggers in the sensor network). Each IoT logger itself is subscribed to a logger-specific topic to trigger the auto-sampler.

The ability to automatically trigger the auto-sampler was made possible by combining the following on-site components (see Fig. 5):

- Physically connecting the auxiliary port of the auto-sampler with an IoT data logger to activate the auto-sampler based on a signal from the IoT logger.
- Extending the electrical circuit and the configuration of the IoT logger to enable the triggering of the auto-sampler and be able to receive information on the program status of the sampling device (e.g. logs of the sampling device).

Fig. 5. Overview of the software and hardware components to implement the remote trigger protocol. The remote triggering protocol includes an internal model (see service, left panel), determining the set points (see middle panel, managed by the broker) for sampling (actuators) based on a model simulation and real-time observations (see inputs, left panel). The MQTT broker handles receiving and sending of messages at the side of the remote server. The IoT datalogger, an in-field device, receives (setpoints) and sends (real-time measurements) messages from/to the MQTT broker. The in-field auto-sampler is physically connected to the IoT datalogger and activates when the IoT datalogger sends a command.

The internal model is the ‘brain’ of the remote trigger protocol and contains the internal logic to define if and when to trigger the auto-sampler. By decoupling the decision model from the IoT logger and the auto-sampler, the internal model can be adjusted or switched without the need of hardware adjustments or a field visit. In the next section, an introduction is given to these decision models.

4.1. Internal model and set points

The aim of the internal model is to define set points for sampling. Ideally, the set points are defined in such a way that the auto-sampler is activated during intense rain events after a certain dry period, as these are the events with higher pollutant loads. An internal model defining the state of the system and the trigger was developed. The system is defined by three states: an idle state, a pending event and an actual event. A state diagram defines these states, and the transition between those states. The transitions are defined by a number of parameters, most importantly the dry period, the event duration and a ‘no cancel window’. These parameters are computed based on rainfall predictions.

Fig. 6 illustrates how set points can be defined. In the panel at the left, a rainfall-volume strategy is illustrated: it assumes a direct response of water flow in the system to the forecasted rainfall and schedules samples based on three key parameters:

- the rain volume trigger: activates sampling when the sum of accumulated volume of forecasted rain exceeds a set threshold);
- the rain intensity trigger: activates sampling when the maximum intensity of forecasted rain exceeds a set threshold;
- “no-event days”, the required amount of dry days before a new set of samples can be taken.

Fig. 6 (right panel) depicts the rainfall-runoff based strategy that uses a runoff model to estimate flow from forecasted rain enabling to implement flow-based sampling. A flow peak trigger is used to initiate sampling when the modelled flow exceeds a certain threshold while also applying the “no-event days” (i.e. dry period) concept. New strategies can be easily defined in the internal model tailoring for specific type of data inputs, available computation models, the chosen regime and the combination of data.

In this study, we use the rainfall-runoff strategy as described in panel B of Figure 6. The rainfall-runoff model used for this case study is a convolution model using the rainfall data with a unit hydrograph, consisting of a triangular function. For calibration of the unit hydrograph parameters, the rainfall gauge data on site and a flow meter in the sewer system were used. The optimum parameters were determined based on using least square regression between measured and modelled flow. Rainfall forecasts (forecast window 2h, temporal resolution 5min) from Buienradar from Nov 2023 – Oct 2024 (<https://www.buienradar.be/>) are used as input for the sample scheduler.

Fig. 6. Illustration of the two strategies (‘equal volume’ or ‘first flush’) exemplified for two internal models (rainfall based, left panel versus rainfall-runoff based, right panel). In the lower graphs (left and right, see red) the timings of the samples is shown. The duration of the high frequency mode on each axis is indicated by the two larger squares (see switch to high/low time resolution). Left panel: only the rainfall forecast is used to schedule samples. No relation between the hydraulics of the system and the rainfall is used. Right panel: the results of the simulated discharge based on the rainfall forecast and a runoff model is used. In the equal volume regime, it is assumed that a sample are planned such they sample an equal volume of the event, whereas in the first flush regime, samples are planned so they fall in the first part of the event.

4.2. Case study

The protocol is tested by sampling the inflow and outflow with two auto-samplers (type Sigma 900) on a pilot in Wetteren (see also <https://stopup.eu/berchem-wetteren>). The urban runoff from a shopping area (shop roofs and parking lots, 5500 m²) is collected in an urban rain shell (URS) and retention tank and purified for reuse as play water. The pilot aims to characterize the water in the retention tank and pollution at different moments during an event.

Fig. 7. (A) Hardware configuration in the field at the outflow during installation showing the IoT Logger for the data communication with the pulse cable to trigger the autosampler. The suction tube takes samples in the retention tank. (B) During the experiment the auto-sampler is put in a closed cabinet and all other components are hidden.

In Fig. 7 (A), the hardware configuration in the field is shown during installation at the outflow of the retention tank. The IoT logger is connected to real-time sensors (water level, electrical conductivity, turbidity) and is responsible for data communication. Via the pulse cable, it can trigger the auto-sampler to take a new sample. The suction tube takes the water from the retention tank to fill the bottles of the auto-sampler. For the experiment, all components are locked and hidden to prevent vandalism and interference with the installation (Fig. 7(B)). When samples are taken by the auto-sampler, the operator gets an automatic warning message (via mail) from the online service to collect the bottles and send these to the lab.

In Table 1, an example of results of a synthetic experiment with the triggering algorithm is shown. It is important to note that these results indicate the feasibility of the triggering algorithm, rather than test the technical approach (for this, see Van Hoey et al., 2024). To compile these results, a subset of four events of interest were selected. The developed triggering algorithms with the rainfall-runoff model, using a flow peak trigger, are used to simulate triggers for these five events, with the rainfall forecasts of these events. The experiment is repeated for three trigger values: 0.5, 2 and 3 m^3s^{-1} . It is shown that the algorithm is sensitive to the chosen threshold: the lower the threshold, the higher the chance for sampling. In addition, it is observed that – in case sampling occurs - the sensitivity towards the number of samples is rather low (between 9 and 13). For details on the selection of these events, we refer to Belachew et al. (submitted).

Table 1: Sensitivity of sampling for four selected events. Each event is tagged by an ‘Event ID’ and the number of executed samples is shown for different thresholds of the flow (flow peak trigger). The approach shows sensitivity towards the trigger, i.e. the higher the trigger value, the lower the chance is that samples are executed.

Event ID	Timing	Parameter (Flow peak trigger (m^3s))	Number of executed samples
1	31/01/2024 23:05 - 01/02/2024 03:50	0.5	13
1	31/01/2024 23:05 - 01/02/2024 03:50	2	0
1	31/01/2024 23:05 - 01/02/2024 03:50	3	0
2	23/07/2024 00: 55 - 23/07/2024 06:45	0.5	12
2	23/07/2024 00: 55 - 23/07/2024 06:45	2	0
2	23/07/2024 00: 55 - 23/07/2024 06:45	3	0
3	30/07/2024 23:35 - 31/07/2024 04:45	0.5	11
3	30/07/2024 23:35 - 31/07/2024 04:45	2	10
3	30/07/2024 23:35 - 31/07/2024 04:45	3	9
4	16/08/2024 06:00 - 16/08/2024 09:55	0.5	13
4	16/08/2024 06:00 - 16/08/2024 09:55	2	10
4	16/08/2024 06:00 - 16/08/2024 09:55	3	0

In this study, it was also explored what the role of proxy sensors could be to refine the triggering algorithm. In Table 2, a summary of the analysis is shown: the laboratory data for chemical oxygen demand (COD), total suspended solids, zinc (Zn) and ammonia (NH_4^+) are compared to the online measurement of Turbidity (COD, TSS and Zn) and Conductivity (NH_4^+). It is important to note that these samples

were taken with an earlier version of the triggering algorithm, only using the rainfall strategy (see left panel,

Fig. 6). The results show that only conductivity is linearly correlated to ammonia on a 5% significance level. In addition, a negative correlation between Zn and COD, on the one hand, and turbidity, on the other, is indicated. As such, current results suggest that the conductivity sensor can be used to further refine the sampling strategy, yet whether to use turbidity as a proxy for this system is inconclusive.

Table 2: Correlation between laboratory and IoT sensor data.

Laboratory analysis	IoT sensor	Linear correlation	p-value
COD (mg/L)	Turbidity (NTU)	-0.07	0.65
TSS (mg/L)	Turbidity (NTU)	0.35	0.06
Zn (mg/L)	Turbidity (NTU)	-0.35	0.02
NH4 (mg N/L)	Conductivity (mS/cm)	0.48	0.0004

Future steps for this case study include a brute force sensitivity analysis (grid search) for a larger range of events, testing a larger precision and range of the flow peak trigger (see Belachew et al., submitted). In addition, an updated strategy needs to be tested in operational mode, and the collected samples can be analyzed in the laboratory to show how variability of these pollutants (not limited to the ones in Table 2) over and in different events can occur. In turn, these laboratory data can be used together with the sensors data to further fine-tune the sampling strategy.

5. Case study Birsfelden

Discharges from combined sewers are a meaningful source of water pollution. Investigations are often based on specific monitoring and sampling campaigns. To capture water quality info despite challenging hydraulic dynamics, e.g. to investigate the relevance of first flush, timely sampling is key. Further, online measurements would be advantageous to retrieve real-time water quality information.

In the Birsfelden case study, we materialize on both aspects by sampling and monitoring the water quality of stormwater retention tank overflows. The investigations are performed in a 45-km² catchment draining to the central WWTP Birs. The WWTP is a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) and can treat a maximum hydraulic flow of 1'000 l/s. The combined sewer system is equipped with 7 stormwater retention tanks with a total storage volume of 14'000 m³. The flow to the WWTP is hydraulically curtailed by weirs in the sewer. During rain events, their height is adjusted to throttle the pass forward flow (PFF), and to divert the excess flow into the storm water retention tanks (SWRT) instead. Note the Pass Forward Flow (PFF) is the instantaneous upstream flow that a Combined Sewer Overflow (CSO) or pumping station can accept. The wastewater collection and retention infrastructure is already equipped with sensors for amongst other filling level, overflows and wastewater flow.

5.1. System monitoring and sampling

For the purpose of our study, we installed additional IoT sensors for electrical conductivity and turbidity in the inlet of the wastewater treatment plant and in the overflow of the three most relevant SWRT, i.e. those three contributing to > 75% of the annual discharge. All sites were also equipped with autosamplers (cf. sampling points 1-4 in Fig. 8).

To start the sampling exactly when an overflow occurs, float switches were used to activate the onsite sampling set-up. The float switches are physical floaters floating on the water surface, and are activated (deactivated) when the water level is higher (lower) than a threshold. In addition, in the case of a spill event in one of the SWRT, also the WWTP inlet was sampled, controlled by a smart triggering protocol developed by Fluves. In this case, the float switch status in the SWRT is monitored through the datalogger by the remote service. When the float switch is activated during an overflow, a SMS socket is activated via a mobile connection to start the pump and autosampler in WWTP inlet. At the same time, the measuring frequency of the sensors is increased from 15 to 1-minute interval. This approach is comparable to the one implemented in the case study of Wetteren, whilst in our case the set point for triggering the sampling is the status of the float switch.

Fig. 8. Scheme of control of the sampling in the WWTP of Birs. At the left part, the scheme shows the sewer network. During a rainfall event, part of the overflow is diverted - as pass forward flow (PFF) by a adjusting weir - to a storm water retention tank to relieve the WWTP of excess wastewater (grey part). The sampling points with IoT sensors (2, 3 and 4) are located at the outlet of the SWRT to the River Birs, and after the sand trap in the WWTP. At sample location 2; an auto sample unit is controlled by means of a SMS socket triggered via an online application (right part, for detail: see text). Simultaneously, IoT sensors measure the conductivity and turbidity at location 2.

5.2. Results

Fig. 9 shows the dynamic of two individual spills of one SWRT and the results for turbidity from online sensors and lab analysis of samples taken (location 2, see Fig. 8). The velocity of the spill in the first event rapidly increases from zero to more than 2000 l/s in the first 30 minutes of the spill (Fig. 9 left, top). This dynamic is mirrored by a comparably fast decline in turbidity (Fig. 9 left, middle). There is also good compliance of lab and online data. A straightforward simplified estimation of the related pollution load by multiplying turbidity with the flow shows that in this event about 50% of the load is accrued in the first 30 minutes of the event (Fig. 9 left, bottom, blue area).

For the second event with a different dynamic and turbidity level, 50% of the pollution load occurs in first 1.25 hours of the event (Fig. 9 right). Both examples show that the reduction of discharge flow from the SWRT for a limited time, possibly by increasing the pass forward flow, could already lead to pollution reduction.

Fig. 9. Examples of overflow behaviour of one of the SWRT during two different rain events. Top: hydraulic dynamic of discharge event; Middle: Development of turbidity in discharge flow, measured with FLUVES online sensors and analysed in selected samples in the lab; bottom: Cumulated share of calculated discharge load over event time, taking turbidity as a proxy.

For a more profound approximation of pollution loads, correlation of sensor data with bulk or priority pollutants is required. An initial data set collected at the SWRT is depicted in Fig. 10. A linear correlation between Turbidity [NTU] and COD [mg/L] could be established ($p > 0.05$), other than in the Wetteren case study which investigated only rainwater runoff.

Fig. 10. Correlation of online measured turbidity and COD (lab analysis) for one of the SWRT. Analysis of individual samples from different overflow events.

6. Conclusions and perspectives for future work

Urban pollution poses significant challenges to aquatic ecosystems, necessitating innovative approaches for effective management. This paper presents findings from three case studies conducted within the StopUP project, a Horizon Europe initiative aimed at mitigating the impacts of urban wastewater on water bodies. A central focus of StopUP is the role of real-time control (RTC) in optimizing urban wastewater and sewer management. A crucial aspect of implementing RTC is the definition of set points and iterative optimization strategies. Typically, these RTC operations rely on a real-time data stream to optimize effectiveness. In StopUP, IoT-based sensors and auto-triggering approaches were employed to collect real-time pollution data, providing valuable insights for RTC implementation. Through three case studies, this paper examines the potential of RTC to enhance pollution monitoring and explores how proxy IoT sensors and auto-triggering techniques contribute to more effective and responsive water management strategies.

The methods established in the Bologna case study set the stage for the development of a prediction model for either EC or turbidity based on a more easily measurable variable, i.e. water level. The key aspect in this case study, opposed to prior studies using point data (e.g. Ji et al., 2022), is the use of methods to identify relations based on continuous data; they further indicate the need to account for a time lag of the order of some hours between the two correlated time series. This implies that a full mathematical model of the sewer system includes integral terms accounting for a memory effect. Overall, the correlation analysis with lag effect developed offers a guideline for modeling sewer systems and adds to proxy sensing by showing how easy-to-monitor variables can be used to estimate harder-to-monitor variables, ultimately reducing the number of sensors needed to real-time monitor water quality. In turn, these proxy IoT sensors can be used to steer real-time control without the need to physically install the higher-cost sensors. Further summarizing, the case study Bologna inspects how proxies can be identified and, in future work, be used to define set points for RTC. Future works should focus on the further exploration of the significance and nature of the identified relations, including more (types of) data, and applying the stated methods with continuous data collected in different conditions and applications (Leigh et al., 2019).

The aim of the Wetteren case study was to introduce and test a novel auto-sampling triggering approach combining real-time observations, rainfall predictions, and near-real-time urban runoff modelling. The main take-away of this study is that automated sampling using an algorithm based on rainfall predictions can aid in improving monitoring efforts for urban systems. The results show a certain sensitivity towards the used parameter, the peak flow trigger, indicating that the used algorithm, using a rainfall/runoff model, can be used to optimize monitoring efforts as a function of monitoring aims. In other words, the strategy can be used to sample for a large or rather limited set of events. Future efforts will focus to further inspect the sensitivity and efficiency of the developed algorithm, see Belachew et al. (submitted). In addition, future efforts should focus on further refining the relation between key pollutant parameters and the used IoT sensors. At this point in the study, the in-situ IoT data were not used to optimize monitoring. Identifying key turnover points in turbidity and conductivity with relation to the key pollutants is essential to develop a method based on real-time IoT sensing, besides using rainfall predictions to proactively identify key events. An advantage of the current technical implementation is its modularity: models used to define the set points can easily be interchanged in order to research different modus operandi (real-time versus in silica, see also Van Hoey et al. (2024)): the current rainfall-runoff approach uses real-time rainfall and flow predictions to define a triggering setpoint. Yet, the implementation allows defining new setpoints based on – for example - water quality predictions, in combination with weather and flow predictions. As such, it makes the application easy to translate to other use cases, given the triggers of the system can be well defined. Even more, if the triggers are not well known, the current application allows to experiment in silica with different types of triggers on historical data, allowing optimizing the application before putting it in ‘real-time’ operation. An example of an in silica experiment would be to include analyzed samples for heavy metals and emerging pollutants to optimize the setpoint definition.

The Birsfelden case study established an event-based smart triggering of sampling and monitoring of SWRT discharges. It allows tracking not only the hydraulic dynamic of different spill events but also the related fast changes in water quality, here turbidity. With sensor data serving as proxy for pollution it would be possible to depict in real-time the load about to be discharged. If connected to the process control system (SCADA) this info can be used for a more dynamic operation of the drainage system, by temporarily adapting flows. This would require defined threshold values for turbidity or conductivity to be integrated in triggering an increase in pass forward flow. Legal discharge limits of WWTP for COD could serve as guide values. They range between 45 to 60 mg/L (Swiss Water Protection Ordinance) and 125 mg/L according to Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive. Further investigations of the correlation of turbidity or electrical conductivity with bulk pollutants (COD), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons or pharmaceutical residue is underway.

The Wetteren and Birsfelden case studies inspect how monitoring efforts can be improved. In particular, the case study Wetteren inspects how urban pollution can be better monitored in terms of a larger range of pollutants (i.e. emerging pollutants). The authors set the combination of proxy sensing and lab analyzed data forward as a way to cost-effectively monitor urban systems. An alternative is the use of expensive in-situ sensors (i.e. lab-in-sensor), yet current technologies for real-time monitoring in-situ emerging contaminants are in an early stage of development, or even more, non-existing. As such, a combination of using cost-efficient and laboratory sensors is currently the most feasible option to inspect urban pollution. The Birsfelden case study inspects how data collected from samples and IoT sensor could potentially be used to improve control strategies. Although the current results are preliminary for operational use, it does show the potential of using

cost-efficient IoT sensors to steer real-time control. Future research should thus further inspect the potential of these data in combination with advanced control algorithms.

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